

Modeling Internet addiction based on identity styles and academic performance: The mediating role of depression

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Abstract:

Introduction: This research aimed to look at the impact of academic success and identity on Internet addiction, with depression acting as a moderator. In terms of design and descriptive-correlation method, the applied form was the least partial least squares, and the research method was structural equation modeling. **Methods:** The statistical population consisted of all students at Tehran universities, and the sample size was 323 people using a random sampling system. Brzonsky (1992) Identity Styles, Chen Internet Addiction (2011), Zhong Depression (1968), and Academic Performance questionnaires were used to gather research results. **Results:** According to the findings of structural equation modeling, academic success and identity explained 25% of the variance in depression and 32% of the variance in Internet addiction. Identity styles and academic success have a substantial negative impact on students' Internet addiction, while loneliness has a significant positive effect. **Conclusion.** Depression acts as a moderator in the relationship between personality forms and academic success and students' Internet addiction.

Addiction to the Internet, Depression, academic performance, cyberspace, identity